

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF DIFFERENT METALS IN ADDITIVE MANUFACTURING AND 3D PRINTING TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract:

With the development of 3D printing (additive manufacturing) technology, different types of forming technologies have different characteristics and classification methods. According to the different deposition states of forming materials, the forming processes of metal parts mainly include SLS technology, SLM technology, LCD technology, 3DP technology and EBM technology. Through the comparison of different metal 3D printing additive manufacturing methods, it can be seen that none of the above mentioned technologies could yet meet the requirements of high accuracy, excellent mechanical properties and low cost. The advantages and disadvantages of each process are studied, and the application fields are significantly introduced.

Key Words: Metal 3D Printing, Additive Manufacturing, SLS Technology, SLM Technology, LCD Technology, 3DP Technology & EBM Technology

1. Introduction:

Additive Manufacturing (AM) is a new digital forming technology based on the discrete-stacking principle. It is known as "manufacturing technology with industrial revolution significance", which greatly shortens the product development cycle and cost. The development of manufacturing industry has very important significance [1].

Different 3D printing (AM) technologies have different characteristics and classification methods. According to the different deposition states of forming materials, the forming process of metal parts is mainly [2-4]: selective laser sintering Selective Laser Sintering, (SLS) technology, Selective laser melting (SLM) technology, laser cladding deposition (LCD) technology, 3D printing (3D Printing, 3DP) technology, Electron Beam Melting (EBM) technology and 3D Micro Welding (3DMW) forming technology.

2. Selective Laser Sintering (SLS) Forming Technology:

Figure 1 is a schematic diagram of the SLS forming principle. The laser scans and sinters the powder material evenly spread on the table surface. After each layer is scanned, the forming piston drops by one layer height, and the subsequent layer forming is continued until the part is completed. Among them, SLS laser rapid prototyping technology has the advantages of multi-material forming; simple forming process; high forming accuracy.

Figure 1: Schematic diagram of SLS forming principle

The forming accuracy of this process can reach an average tolerance of 0.05 ~ 2.5 mm. And without designing the support structure, the unsintered powder can be directly used as the support for the suspended layer in the forming process. Therefore, the material utilization rate is high, which is the highest utilization rate among several common AM processes and the cheaper process.

The main disadvantages of selective laser sintering (SLS) technology are:

- Poor surface quality. The forming of the parts is made of powdered raw materials by heating and melting to achieve layer-by-layer bonding. Therefore, the surface of the parts is strictly powdery and therefore the surface is rough;
- The mechanical properties are poor. The prototype structure is loose and porous, and the density of the parts is low, so the mechanical properties are poor.

3. Selective Laser Melting (SLM) Technology:

The metal materials used in SLM technology mainly include iron-based alloys, TiC4 alloys, 316L stainless steel powder, copper alloys, titanium alloys, tool steels, etc. [5]. Many of these materials need to be imported. The surface forming accuracy can reach 30 - 60 μm , and the dimensional accuracy can reach ± 0.1 mm. The metal powder can be completely melted to obtain a fully dense structure with good mechanical properties (Table 1).

Table 1: Mechanical properties of different materials in SLM

Material	Tensile Strength / MPa	Elongation /%	Hardness /HB	Surface finish / μm	Accuracy / $\pm\text{mm}$	Density /%
Stainless Steel	480~520	10~15	220~250	Rz30~60	<0.1	100
Tool Steel	780~840	2~3	50~54	Rz30~60	<0.1	100
Ti-6Al-4V	1200~1400	1~2	380~420	Rz 30~60	<0.1	100

4. Laser Cladding Deposition (LCD) Technology:

This technology can use iron-based alloys, stainless steel powder, copper alloys, titanium alloys, etc. as molding materials, and also can use WC / Co, TiC4, VC and other hard metals and Al₂O₃, TiO₂ and other ceramic materials to form, which is a complex part of an effective method for rapid prototyping. In addition, this technology can use the laser to generate instantaneous high energy on the surface of the workpiece to make the molten powder material and the base layer metallurgical combination, and the residual heat generated by traditional welding processes (such as: tungsten gas shielded welding, argon arc welding, etc.) Low stress is an ideal technique for repairing damaged blades, steam turbines, and turbine disks.

5. Three-Dimensional Printing (3D Printing, 3DP) Technology:

The 3DP process uses a liquid binder. The liquid binder is sprayed on the powder layer laid on the table through the nozzle. After the area sprayed with the binder is solidified, the metal powder is bonded together. Formed parts are not "pure" metal parts in the true sense. The density of "green parts" is about 60% [6]. Figure 2 shows the schematic diagram of the 3DP process. Figure 2 Schematic diagram of 3DP forming principle

Figure 2: Schematic diagram of 3DP forming principle

The 3DP process is similar to the SLS process in that powder materials (ceramic powder, metal powder, etc.) are "printed" on the material powder through nozzles with adhesive (such as silica gel), rather than being connected by sintering. Therefore, the parts have low strength and must be processed afterwards. 3DP technology can improve the forming accuracy by reducing the powder diameter and the thickness of the powder layer, and the precision of its parts is also very high. Molded parts need to adopt a post-treatment process similar to indirect SLS to increase the density, and molded parts are also mostly used in injection molds and other low-load situations. Because there is no expensive equipment such as laser, the cost of the equipment is much lower than other Metal forming equipment such as laser and electron beam [7].

6. Electron Beam Melting (EBM) Technology:

The principle of EBM technology is: in a vacuum environment, the metal beam or metal powder material is melted by the electron beam welding process, and then deposited in layers according to the set path to form a metal part.

A wide range of materials that can be used for electron beam free forming, such as tool steel, titanium alloy, nickel alloy, and even refractory molybdenum alloy and other conductive metal materials, can be used for electron beam deposition and forming. Electron beam can also be used for metal deposition with high reflection effect on light energy: For example, at room temperature, Ti-6Al-4V material reflects the laser light more seriously. Using laser sintering process, the energy utilization rate is very low. The reflectivity of the electron beam is only about 10%, which has a high energy utilization rate [8-10].

However, the electron beam deposition requires a vacuum environment with a high degree of vacuum, and the cost of the equipment is expensive; and the electron beam will be accompanied by the emission of gamma rays during the deposition process. If the device design is unreasonable, it will cause radiation leakage and environmental pollution. In addition, the electron beam can only deposit conductive materials, not plastics, ceramics and other non-conductive materials [11].

Table 2 is a comparison of additive manufacturing methods for metal 3D printing. It can be seen that no single technology can meet the requirements of high accuracy, excellent mechanical performance, and low cost. The advantages and disadvantages of each process are obvious, and the application fields are significantly different.

Table 2: Comparison of additive manufacturing technologies

Density	> 90%	> 90%	> 90%	> 90%	> 60%	> 90%
Equipment Model	self-made	Sintersation HiQ	MCP SLM Realizer II	LENS850-R	SR-2	EBM S12
material	Powder/rod/wire	powder	powder	powder	powder	Powder / wire
Material Ruler (Titanium alloy as an example) μm	Not restricted	100	20-50	100-150	100-150	100-150
Heat source / power	Induction / 25 kW	Laser / < 100 W	laser /200W~1 kW	laser / > 2 kW	None (adhesive)	Electron beam /3.5 kW
Maximum shaped piece size /mm	Not restricted	800×800	500×500	3000×3000	500×500	400×400
Application area	Parts repair, nested components, etc.	Aerospace mold parts, etc.	Mold, medical treatment, electricity	Mold, medical treatment, electricity	Mold	Parts repair, biomedical

7. Conclusion:

These characteristics of metal 3D printing additive manufacturing technology meet the needs of the rapid, personalized and flexible development of modern manufacturing. Therefore, the research on the use of direct metal 3D printing has become a hot spot in AM research. Medical, aviation and other manufacturing fields have been widely used and have shown very good application prospects [16-17].

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